

THE ESSENCE OF STUDYING THE WORK OF BERDAK, A CLASSIC EXAMPLE OF KARAKALPAK LITERATURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403280>

Abstract. *This article reflects on the life and socio-political situation of the people in Berdak's works. The poet embodied in his work about the daily life of the hardworking people, the oppression of the colonists against the Karakalpak people, and the oppression of the people as a result of the unjust actions of the officials. The poet aims to develop the country by educating the youth in the spirit of patriotism.*

Keywords: *Berdak's life and work, literary heritage, manuscripts.*

Every nation has its great children who present its identity, national status and dignity to the world. The immortal legacy left by them determines not only the past, but also the present and the future of the nation. We will always appreciate the great Berdak poet not only as a Karakalpak, but as one of the most honored children of our nation. Life itself has repeatedly proven that a free and prosperous society cannot be built in any country in the world where science has not developed. It has been emphasized in the works of our writers that the link between the past and the future is the intellectual potential of young people. The land of Karakalpak has surprised us all with its unique, rich and high art, which has no analogues in the world. When talking about Berdak, a folk poet with his own direction, style and opinion of Karakalpak literature, Berdak, son of Kargaboy, was born on November 9, 1827, in the first quarter of the 19th century, on November 9, 1827. He was born in a peasant family. Berdak was an intellectual of his time, a person with unique deep thinking, more intelligent than his contemporaries and a person with a high position. He received his primary education first at the village school and then at the madrasa. Alisher deeply read the works of Navoi, Fuzuli, Makhtumquli and Karakalpak poet Kunkhoja, and learned from them. He knew history, folklore, and oral art well. Berdak's lyrical poems and epics express the social nature of the Karakalpak people in the 18th and 19th centuries. He evaluates the events and social relations of his time as an intelligent poet. The ideas of equality, humanity, justice and patriotism are put forward in his works. In Berdak's work, the main themes of the working people's situation are "Not what happened", "Tax", "This year", "My life" and others.

The poet dreamed of selfless fighters for the truth, for the happiness and future of the working masses. In his poems, he wrote and composed many verses on "For the people", "I need it" and other topics. The poet proudly sings about national heroes in his historical works "Avlodlar", "Omongeldi", "Azadosbi", "Ernazarbi". Berdak's work "Avlodlar" is a chronicle of historical events, the common events in the lives of the Karakalpak people and other Turkic peoples are recorded, and the opinions about the origin of tribes and peoples are expressed. Berdak exposes the lies of some prominent priests in poems such as "Yakhshiraq", "Shakilli" and other works. He defends women's rights, calls on young people to love the motherland and reach the heights of enlightenment.

There are various legends about the birth of the poet, who lamented that "the sea did not give him fish...". Today's generation, reading these lines, may think that even at that time, Orol retreated. No, both the sea and the river were full of fish, but the ships and hunting weapons were

in the hands of the oppressors, and in some places the poor were forbidden to hunt. The poet, who asked God for the sustenance of the poor from the river and the sea full of fish, and called on his compatriots to be patient and forbearing, sought justice and freedom from this world. Poet Utesh, the contemporary nephew of Berdak, who suffered a lot in his time, said that Berdak's mother was paid a sum of melon seeds...It is consistent with the requirements for works of art in the section "Arousing sympathy and horror". Indeed, "In poetry, it is better to describe the unnatural in a believable way than to describe the natural in a way that one cannot believe," wrote Aristotle. It is worth showing the poet's love and thirst for knowledge as an example to the younger generation. The great poet of Karakalpak classical literature, Berdak Kargaboy son, can get a lot of meaning from the poems that have reached us. In all of Berdak's creations, one can get a complete picture of the living conditions of the people, the social and political life of that time. In his works, the poet tried to comfort the people with his songs about the plight of the people, poverty. The more we talk about Berdak's life and work, the less we can say.

Therefore, it is necessary to widely promote Berdak's work among our youth, translate his works into Uzbek, and introduce the young generation to our people. In honor of the brilliant memory of the famous literary and artistic person, the people's poet, the streets, garden avenues, and cinemas of Nukus and other cities were named after Berdak. Karakalpak State Musical Theater named after Berdak, one of the most prestigious theaters in our country, is famous not only in our country, but also abroad. Berdak is a great folk singer who is able to convey to the reader the pains and sufferings of a sensitive poet, as well as providing warmth that is a salve for the grassy pain of the people. The poet, who understood this well, wrote works and poems with a special emphasis on the points that the reader should pay attention to in order to gain knowledge by referring to the essence of experiences in his poems. Of course, many examples like the above can be cited. But it should be noted that it is not their number, but their weight. In general, Berdak's poetry occupies a special place in the history of our literature. Therefore, his exemplary life, moral heritage in his works and writings are of great importance in the development of high human qualities in the hearts of young people and in the education of a well-rounded generation. If we study the rich historical and spiritual heritage of our ancestors and do not fight against various dangers with determination and consistency in time, various harmful currents may enter our country.

For this purpose, if we translate the poems of Berdak's life and works from the works of our writers into other languages than the Karakalpak language, the youth of our multilingual nation will read them so that our youth will be drawn into the vortex of the pursuit of creativity and science in the epics of his poems and the ideas of serving the people. In Berdak's poems, he puts forward such ideas as parents, family, duties and responsibilities to the country, and patriotism. In order to protect young people from today's internet, it is necessary to translate the works of patriotic writers like Berdak, poems and literary books in different languages into our mother tongue, Uzbek. In order to prevent young people from becoming selfish people who live only for one day, they should be occupied with literature, art, and sports. Revealing the true nature of Berdak's work and his efforts to restore his pure name contradicted the instructions of the former center, slanderous stones were thrown at Najim Davqoraev. The scientist died on the verge of being expelled from the party and imprisoned. After that, candidacy and doctoral theses were defended in the literary and scientific studies devoted to Berdak's work, about the harmony of his work with the ideas of Komfirka, his patriotism and his philosophical-atheistic views. By the time of independence, unnecessary debates about Berdak's work stopped, and new aspects of the poet's

legacy were opened. Revealing the true nature of Berdak's work and his efforts to restore his pure name contradicted the instructions of the former center, slanderous stones were thrown at Najim Davqoraev. The scientist died on the verge of being expelled from the party and imprisoned. After that, candidacy and doctoral theses were defended in the literary and scientific studies devoted to Berdak's work, about the harmony of his work.

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